

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of aliphatic alcohols by quinolinium chlorochromate

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Manuscript received 7 August 1998, revised 4 January 1999, accepted 13 January 1999

The kinetics of oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols by quinolinium chlorochromate (QCC) to the corresponding aldehydes have been studied. The reaction is first order each in the concentrations of QCC, alcohol and H^+ . Oxidation of $[1,1-^2H_2]$ ethanol indicates the presence of primary kinetic isotope effect. The reaction rates have been determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated. With an increase in the amount of acetic acid in its aqueous mixture, the rate decreases. The reaction does not induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. A mechanism involving hydride ion transfer has been proposed.

A number of reports on the mechanism of oxidation of several alcohols by halochromates of nitrogen containing heterocyclic cationic compounds are available¹. Quinolinium chlorochromate is an efficient reagent for the selective oxidation of primary alcohols to yield the carbonyl compounds². The oxidation of alcohols with several oxidants may follow different mechanistic pathways. The paper presents the result of kinetic studies of 15 aliphatic primary alcohols in dipolar protic solvent (60% aqueous-acetic acid).

Results and Discussion

The reaction is first order each in [QCC] and [alcohol]. Further, the first order rate constants (k_1) are independent of the initial concentration of QCC. Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics are observed with respect to the concentration of alcohols (Table 1). A plot of $1/[alcohol]$ against $1/k_1$ is linear (r 0.999) and does not pass through the origin. A positive intercept shows that a 1 : 1 complex is formed prior to the rate-limiting step between QCC and alcohol. The complex subsequently decomposes into products,

The above mechanism leads to the following rate equation,

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_2 K [\text{QCC}] [\text{alcohol}]}{1 + K [\text{alcohol}]} \quad (3)$$

The values of the equilibrium constant (K) and the rate of decomposition of the complex (k_2) were obtained from the slope and intercept of the double reciprocal plots respectively. K is very small and it is below the detectable level as was observed in the oxidation of phenylmethyl sulphide with pyridinium chlorochromate in protic solvent³.

Table 1. Effect of concentration of reactants on reaction rates at 303 K in acid media

$[H^+] = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Acetic acid = 60% (v/v)			
$10^2[\text{Ethanol}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^3[\text{QCC}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^4 k_1$ s^{-1}	
1.0	2.0	1.35	
2.0	2.0	2.64	
2.0	2.0	2.50 ^a	
2.0	2.0	2.68 ^b	
3.0	2.0	3.92	
4.0	2.0	5.14	
5.0	2.0	6.51	
6.0	2.0	7.67	
7.0	2.0	9.02	
8.0	2.0	10.5	
6.0	3.0	7.70	
6.0	4.0	7.63	
6.0	5.0	7.53	
6.0	6.0	7.76	

^aContained 0.05 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile. ^bContained 0.02 mol dm⁻³ quinoline.

The increase in $[H^+]$ increases the reaction rate and shows a direct first order dependence on $[H^+]$ (Table 2). This proves the involvement of a protonated chromium(vi) species in the rate-limiting step. Involvement of such species is well established in the chromic acid oxidation of alcohols⁴. The rate of acid-catalysed oxidation of alcohol decreases with an increase in the dielectric constant of the medium (Table 3). A plot of $\log k_1$ against inverse of dielectric constant is linear with a positive slope suggesting an interaction between a positive ion and a dipole⁵. This confirms the involvement of protonated chromium(vi) species in the rate-determining step. It is further confirmed by the constancy of rate constant with the change in ionic strength. A plot of $\log k_1$ against $\sqrt{\mu}$ gives a linear plot with zero slope.

Table 2. Effect of concentration of acid on reaction rates at 303 K

[Ethanol] = 0.06 mol dm⁻³, [QCC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, Acetic acid = 60%(v/v)

[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0
10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)	1.38	4.64	7.67	11.2	14.4	17.7	20.6	23.5

Table 3. Effect of concentration of solvent on reaction rates at 303 K in acid media

[Ethanol] = 0.06 mol dm⁻³, [QCC] = 0.002 mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.7 mol dm⁻³

Acetic acid-water (%, v/v)	30	40	50	60	70
Dielectric constant	72.0	63.3	56.0	45.5	38.5
10 ⁴ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)	21.9	2.73	3.89	7.66	13.7

The oxidation of [1,1-²H₂] ethanol was studied to ascertain the importance of cleavage of the α-C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The result showed the presence of a primary kinetic isotope effect (k_H/k_D 3.93 at 303 K).

The oxidation of ethanol under nitrogen atmosphere failed to induce polymerization to the monomer acrylonitrile. This indicates that one-electron oxidation is quite unlikely. In control experiments, the concentration of QCC did not show any appreciable change. The rate of oxidation was not affected by an addition of quinoline (upto 0.05 mol dm⁻³). The variation of the concentration of the alcohol was studied at different temperatures (293–323 K). The activation parameters for the decomposition of the complex were computed (Table 4). A linear correlation is obtained (r 0.999) when $\log k_2$ (323 K) is plotted against $\log k_2$ (293 K) for the fifteen alcohols. This indicates that all the alcohols were oxidised by the same mechanism. The rates of the decomposition of the complexes failed to show satisfactory correlation with either the polar or the steric substituent constants⁷ or for the dual substituent parameter⁸. However, there is negative polar reaction and steric substituent constants. This suggests a hydride ion transfer in the rate-determining step. A similar conclusion was reached in the oxidation of alcohols by pyridinium chlorochromate⁹.

Mechanism : The observed results suggest a hydride transfer in the rate-determining step. A hydrogen abstraction mechanism is unlikely in view of the failure to induce polymerization of acrylonitrile. The hydride ion transfer may take place either by the formation of an ester intermediate or by an acyclic process¹⁰. The kind of mechanism

can be ascertained with the help of kinetic isotope effect¹¹. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethanols, fitted to equation (4),

$$\frac{k_H}{k_D} = \frac{A_H}{A_D} e^{\frac{\Delta E_{\ddagger}}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

show direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state¹². The activation energy difference (ΔE_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (~3.2 kJ mol⁻¹) and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. In a concerted sigmatropic reaction a cyclic hydride transfer takes place. It is a highly symmetrical process involving linear transfer of hydro-gen¹³. Such observation has been made in the oxidation of alcohols by chromium(vi)¹⁴. Based on these facts the mechanism proposed is presented in Scheme 1. The chromate ester intermediate will be better stabilized in the less polar medium and will enhance the oxidation rate as has been observed in this reaction.

Scheme 1

Experimental

The alcohols were commercial products and distilled before use. [1,1-²H₂] Ethanol¹⁵ and QCC² were prepared by the reported methods. The purity of QCC was checked by estimating chromium(vi) iodometrically. Acetic acid was purified by the reported procedure¹⁶. All other reagents (AnalaR) were used as such.

Product analyses were carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, ethanol (4.6 g, 0.1 mol) and QCC (4.98 g, 0.02 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml of the solvent (60% v/v aqueous acetic acid) and kept in the dark for ~12 h to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then treated with an excess (200 cm³) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl and kept in a refrigerator for 12 h. The solvent was removed and the precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallised from alcohol and again weighed. The yields of DNP were 11.3 g (84%) and 10.1 g (75%) before and after recrystallisation respectively. The product was identical (m.p. and m.m.p.) with an authentic sample of the DNP of acetaldehyde.

The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of alcohol with respect to QCC. The solvent was 60% (v/v) aqueous acetic

Table 4. Temperature effect and thermodynamic parameters of QCC oxidation of aliphatic alcohols

Alcohol	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ⁻³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)			323 K	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger
	293 K	303 K	313 K		(± 1.0) kJ mol ⁻¹	(± 4.0) JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	(± 2.5) kJ mol ⁻¹
Methanol	1.56	2.78	4.90	9.45	44.3	148	89.1
Ethanol	7.12	13.1	23.3	41.8	43.8	137	83.5
Propan-1-ol	12.1	21.9	36.6	61.5	39.8	146	84.0
Butan-1-ol	27.9	48.5	93.6	148	42.0	132	82.0
Pentan-1-ol	17.8	32.6	61.5	108	45.0	125	82.9
Hexan-1-ol	16.4	29.8	54.4	93.9	43.3	131	83.0
Heptan-1-ol	15.2	28.6	51.3	84.5	42.5	134	83.1
Octan-1-ol	14.6	27.0	49.6	80.2	42.4	135	83.3
2-Methylpropan-1-ol	24.5	46.8	88.6	155	46.0	119	82.1
3-Methylbutan-1-ol	22.1	41.5	76.4	138	45.4	122	82.2
2-Ethylbutan-1-ol	17.3	32.4	60.8	106	45.2	124	82.8
2,2-Dimethylpropan-1-ol	33.8	62.4	115	208	45.1	119	81.2
2-Chloroethanol	2.47	4.23	7.60	14.2	43.2	148	88.0
2-Phenylethanol	4.63	9.26	17.4	32.5	48.4	130	87.8
2-Methoxyethanol	7.52	13.8	28.7	50.5	48.1	127	86.6
[1,1- ² H ₂] Ethanol	1.74	3.32	6.04	11.8	47.5	136	89.4

acid. The reactions were followed iodometrically at constant temperature (± 0.1 K). The pseudo-first order rate constant (k_1) was evaluated from the linear least-squares plot of $\log [\text{QCC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed the rate constants to be reproducible within $\pm 4\%$. The second order rate constant was obtained by the relation, $k_2 = k_1/[\text{alcohol}]$.

The oxidation of ethanol by QCC in aqueous acetic acid gave acetaldehyde in high yield (>80%). Excess of QCC was allowed to react with ethanol (0.05 mol) and the unreacted chromium(vi) estimated. The overall reaction corresponds to

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